

The Coupling Constant Equation and Weak Interaction Left Orientation – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constant equation in its first and second representations, i.e. net variations and spin, It than becomes vividly clear that the weak interaction is different than all the other interactions in the series, and would be negative left oriented spin wise. Such an orientation is related to being excluded from the prime critical line, after being added the Majestic (3). Such an orientation could also be a feature of the strong interaction, as it is not on the prime critical line as well, and similarly is located left to it.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (2)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (4)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8 + (1) \\
& [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \\
& [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \\
& [(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \\
& \dots \\
& [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \\
& [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \\
& [(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Notice that each term in the series within the Parenthesis is prime $\rightarrow 123, 843, 9243 \dots$ as one did not calculate the entire series he is going to assume that is would be true concerning each higher element in the series. We are leaving out the net variation in this part. Notice that the only term which is not a prime after added the Majestic (3) or spin (1/2) is the second element in the series, in which we associate with the weak interaction.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] = 27 \tag{5}$$

As the series is increasing and each term inside the parenthesis is creating a higher prime than the previous element, in order of weak interaction to be of the same nature of the rest of the forces, we would need that the sum of the parenthesis to be a prime, we look for the closest higher prime:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] \rightarrow 29 \tag{6}$$

So in order to be like the rest of the forces. Meaning to have a prime inside a parenthesis, it lacks a certain amount of variation. If we associate each interaction to be invariant to direction – and the Cause of such a trait could be the prime term inside the parenthesis, than the weak interaction would differ by its nature.

The fact that the term inside the parenthesis is not on the critical line of the primes, but left to it, can explain why the weak interaction is left oriented and differ by its nature by the rest in terms of its spin. We have proved that the majestic (3) is really a different representation of Spin, which destabilizes clusters of perfect variations causing the tN_V o appear, which overall yield a propagation of a Boson from the fermion, and therefore gives us the beautiful series of coupling constants. If all the Terms on the critical line of primes are yielding interactions that are invariant to direction, than one could predict the weak interaction to be spin oriented to the left by the ratio (2), since the strong interaction is also not on the critical line, such orientation could exist in its regards as well.

$$27 - 29 = -2 \tag{7}$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{2} - 2\right) = -\frac{3}{2} \tag{8}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)